

Sketching sounds: an exploratory study on sound-shape associations

Detailed description of audio and sketch feature analysis

This document provides additional information about the audio and sketch analysis described in the paper *Sketching Sounds: an exploratory study on sound-shape associations*. Descriptions of features and resulting values are presented in Section 1 for audio features and in Section 2 for sketch features.

1 Audio Features

Audio features were extracted using the Librosa library [1] and timbre models by Pearce et al. [2].

1.1 Librosa Features

The following features were extracted using the Librosa library [1] with a FFT window size of 2048 and hop length of 512. The mean value calculated from all windows is reported. The perceptual interpretation is based on research by Peeters [3].

- **Spectral Flatness:** A measure of the noisiness/sinusoidality of a sound defined by the ratio of the geometric mean to the arithmetic mean of its spectrum.
- **Spectral Centroid:** A measure of the centre of mass of a spectrum. A higher value suggests a brighter sound.
- **Root Mean Square Power (RMS):** A measure for the amplitude of the audio signal that corresponds with its perceived loudness.
- **Zero Crossing Rate:** The number of times a signal crosses the zero axis. Periodic sounds tend to have a small value and noisy sounds a high value.

1.2 RMS Slope

In addition, the feature **RMS Slope** was calculated from Librosa's RMS value to measure the irregularity of a sound stimulus. First, a low-pass filter was applied to smoothen small changes in amplitude. Then, the mean gradient value between local maxima and minima pairs was calculated. To focus on amplitude changes within the sound, the first and last transition between extrema associated with the attack and decay were disregarded. A higher RMS Slope value corresponds with a more intersected sound. While the measure provided meaningful results in this study, it might need refinement to be universally applicable. Figure 1 shows a visualisation of the process.

1.3 Timbre Models

The Python implementation of the timbre models by Pearce et al. [2] were used to extract perceptually informed features. **Hardness**, **Depth**, **Brightness**, **Roughness**, **Warmth**, **Sharpness** and **Boominess** were used in this study.

Figure 1: Visualisation of the RMS Slope. The light-grey line shows the original RMS envelope, the blue line shows the signal after low-pass filtering and the red line shows the gradients between extrema.

1.4 Extracted Values

Table 1 shows the the values extracted from all ten sound stimuli.

	Flatness Mean	Centroid Mean	RMS Mean	RMS Slope	Zero Crossing Mean	Hardness	Depth	Brightness	Roughness	Warmth	Sharpness	Boominess
Crackles	$4.1 \cdot 10^{-2}$	1728	0.032	21	0.035	55	28	60	52	41	48	17
Telephonic	$1.0 \cdot 10^{-3}$	543	0.157	5	0.013	34	67	43	50	54	28	41
Strings	$3.9 \cdot 10^{-5}$	1042	0.151	10	0.020	42	57	52	52	54	35	33
String Grains	$1.9 \cdot 10^{-3}$	1177	0.107	22	0.031	52	40	56	56	49	37	25
Subbass	$1.5 \cdot 10^{-8}$	206	0.416	1	0.002	34	77	36	47	65	34	47
Noise	$2.9 \cdot 10^{-1}$	7915	0.086	34	0.144	81	44	81	81	29	68	22
Piano	$4.5 \cdot 10^{-7}$	542	0.051	1	0.013	42	65	49	40	54	31	42
Impact	$2.8 \cdot 10^{-4}$	1047	0.097	8	0.011	65	77	60	49	51	49	39
Processed Guitar	$1.7 \cdot 10^{-3}$	229	0.344	3	0.002	30	80	39	40	63	37	46
Electric Guitar	$4.5 \cdot 10^{-6}$	1295	0.305	5	0.022	47	56	56	56	50	42	34

Table 1: Sound features extracted from all sound stimuli. For Librosa features, the mean values of all windows are reported.

2 Sketch Features

Sketch features were extracted directly from the data through simple arithmetic operations, an adaptation of Bresenham’s rasterisation algorithm [4] and the ShortStraw algorithm [5, 6]. Each sketch was saved in the format:

```
#Sketch array
  [#Stroke 1 array
    [#Recorded stroke points
      [x0,x1,x2,...], #x positions
      [y0,y1,y2,...], #y positions
      [t0,t1,t2,...], #timestamps
    ],
    #More Stroke arrays
    [...],
    [...],
    ...
  ]
```

2.1 Basic Features

Basic features can be calculated with simple arithmetic operations.

- **Number of Strokes:** Counting the number of stroke arrays gives the number of strokes.
- **Average Length:** The length of a stroke is calculated by summing the euclidean distances between consecutive points. The mean value from all strokes in one sketch is reported.
- **Average Time:** Subtracting the timestamp of the first point from the timestamp of the last point in a stroke gives the total time it took to complete that stroke. The mean value from all strokes in one sketch is reported.
- **Average Speed:** Dividing the drawing time of a stroke by its length defines its drawing speed. The mean value from all strokes in one sketch is reported.

2.2 Intersections

An intersection was detected when a stroke reaches a pixel that has already been filled by a previous stroke. Bresenham’s rasterisation algorithm [4] was used to generate a bitmap from the sketch data, while tracking how often each pixel is filled. An example can be seen in Figure 2a.

2.3 ShortStraw Algorithm

The original ShortStraw algorithm [5] was used to find corner points that were divided into **obtuse**, **right** and **acute angles**. To account for noise, a right angle was defined as $85^\circ < \alpha < 95^\circ$. The extended ShortStraw algorithm [6] was used to find curve points that were divided into **wide** and **narrow curve** shape as described in Figure 2c.

(a) Intersection detection using an adaptation of Bresenham’s rasterisation algorithm [4]. The size of the red dots corresponds to the number of intersections at that point.

(b) Feature point detection with the shortstraw algorithm [5, 6]. Stroke start/end points are coloured green/blue and corner/curve points are coloured red/yellow.

(c) Different curve shapes according to Xiong and LaViola [6]. For this study, a narrow curve was defined with $\alpha < 90^\circ$ and a wide curve with $\alpha \geq 90^\circ$.

Figure 2: Sketch feature extraction

2.4 Extracted Values

Table 2 shows the mean sketch feature values from all participant sketches for all ten sound stimuli. Intersection, corner and curve points are reported relative to the total length of a sketch to provide a better measure of the dominance of these features.

	Number of Strokes	Average Length [px]	Average Time [ms]	Average Speed [px/ms]	Intersections [1/100px]	Narrow Curves [1/100px]	Wide Curves [1/100px]	Obtuse Angles [1/100px]	Right Angles [1/100px]	Acute Angles [1/100px]
Crackles	10.5	471	2796	0.22	1.78	0.55	0.60	0.94	0.22	0.67
Telephonic	6.0	1091	4613	0.27	1.05	0.16	0.37	0.55	0.08	0.26
Strings	3.9	900	4379	0.26	0.31	0.10	0.23	0.28	0.06	0.09
String Grains	10.1	914	3340	0.28	1.48	0.24	0.21	0.58	0.15	0.54
Subbass	4.5	1328	6154	0.23	0.92	0.17	0.43	0.51	0.08	0.30
Noise	12.8	1816	3540	0.57	2.37	0.32	0.22	0.61	0.16	0.56
Piano	3.8	586	3020	0.29	0.61	0.06	0.31	0.20	0.02	0.06
Impact	7.2	1239	3313	0.51	1.12	0.14	0.28	0.24	0.05	0.31
Processed Guitar	4.3	1124	4707	0.33	0.43	0.17	0.23	0.49	0.09	0.22
Electric Guitar	5.3	1121	4561	0.33	0.93	0.12	0.12	0.35	0.08	0.40

Table 2: Sketch features. The mean value from all participants is presented for each sound stimulus.

References

- [1] B. McFee, C. Raffel, D. Liang, D. P. Ellis, M. McVicar, E. Battenberg, and O. Nieto, “librosa: Audio and music signal analysis in python,” in *Proceedings of the 14th python in science conference*, vol. 8, pp. 18–25, Citeseer, 2015.
- [2] A. Pearce, T. Brookes, and R. Mason, “Modelling Timbral Hardness,” *Applied Sciences*, vol. 9, no. 3, p. 466, 2019.
- [3] G. Peeters, “A large set of audio features for sound description (similarity and classification) in the cuidado project,” *CUIDADO Ist Project Report*, vol. 54, no. 0, pp. 1–25, 2004.
- [4] J. E. Bresenham, “Algorithm for computer control of a digital plotter,” *IBM Systems journal*, vol. 4, no. 1, pp. 25–30, 1965.
- [5] A. Wolin, B. Eoff, and T. Hammond, “Shortstraw: A simple and effective corner finder for polylines,” in *SBM*, pp. 33–40, 2008.
- [6] Y. Xiong and J. J. LaViola Jr, “Revisiting shortstraw: improving corner finding in sketch-based interfaces,” in *Proceedings of the 6th Eurographics Symposium on Sketch-Based Interfaces and Modeling*, pp. 101–108, 2009.